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Session 5 live-captioning, Thursday, 22 June 2023:

[Surveys of nearby galaxies](#)

Myung Gyoon Lee: Stellar populations, and observation cosmology with Roman and JWST

Welcome to session five of the Roman workshop happening here this week. We are going to get started today with the first talk which is by Myung Gyoon Lee from Seoul National University calling in from Seoul. Are you ready to get started? Myung: Yes, I am. We see your screen but your face is very blurry on your video. Myung: The light from the ceiling. That's much better. We can see you now. You have 25 minutes. Myung: Thank you. Good morning, everyone. I am Myung Gyoon Lee from Seoul National University in Korea. Today, I'm going to talk about stellar population is an observational cosmology with Roman and JWST. Today, I will focus on cosmology based on galaxies in the local universe. Roman for this local cosmology, first of all, high-resolution imaging of galaxies. We can use resolved stars and star clusters in a galaxy. Second, a very wide field of view imaging so we can cover large galaxies or a galaxy clusters or we can catch many small ones in the field at once. From the images of galaxies obtained with Roman, we can derive diagrams of stars and star clusters in galaxies. We can derive the age and metallicity and star formation history and metal enrichment history of multiple populations and their special distributions in a given galaxy. Then, from this, you can tell how small to large galaxies form and evolve in the history of the universe. Stellar population is also can be used as a tool. For example, you can use to limit the luminosity of the population as a standard counsel for cosmology. Fluctuations are some variable responses or whatever. In addition, you can utilize the special distribution of a population to trace baryon and dark matter. Today, I'm going to introduce some examples science cases in the local universe. First of all, the precision because Margaret Way of the local universe, then one example with dark matter in the Hubble flow. Third one is testing models with broad galaxies and then origin of intracluster and hero right. Finally, globular cluster mapping of galaxy clusters. The first, precision because Margaret Fay of the local universe. An excellent example was given by extragalactic distance database. This is the most extensive catalog of the distances to nongalaxies derived with various distance indicators. However, it's far from being complete and then there are many more galaxies, mostly with low surface brightness, waiting to be found and measured in the local universe. We use a precise general to measure distances to any local galaxies. It will be the keeper of the written

brand. a candle for measuring any types of resolve galaxies. This TRGB is the best tool for precision cosmography. Looking at this census of ten census, TRGB is a robust candle in the era of space telescopes including Hubble space telescope. A number of TRGB distances with a tasty long larger than 500 and most of them are closer than 20 mega part six of from our intergalactic distance database project. Also small number of more distant galaxies up to 30 mega parsecs. The histogram of the nongalaxies in the distance range, between ten and 30 is almost empty. This pot is supposed to be filled with Roman and JWST. Precision cosmography with TRGB. You can derive distances to every local galaxy including known and unknown in the Roman and JWST. You can go further, and majority of them, new, small, faint dwarf galaxies like ultra-faint boards, most of which were not covered by HST. With Roman and JWST, you can derive a precise 3D map of the local universe which can be used for diverse cosmography project. One example is given here. Dark matter in the Hubble flow. One example is for Virgo cluster. 2020, a paper with the title determination of the local H_0 and dark matter is from Virgo cluster in fall using TRGB distances. Oops. Galaxies around the Virgo cluster are affected by the gravity of Virgo, showing infall motion toward the Virgo. Their motion in the universe can be described, assuming a spherical shell with videos are moving radially in a cluster with M by this simple equation. You can derive the relation like this. Here, zero velocity radius where the cluster is separated from the Hubble flow and the mass is given as a function of R_0 and H_0 . If we have a velocity and distance of infaLL galaxies, we can determine both the value of H_0 and the mass of the cluster. This is strange. Sorry about this one. Here are examples of 33 galaxies with velocity and TRGB senses which are located in front of Hubble, collected from various literatures. The locations in the sky around Virgo. They are located further from the radius, mostly. Come on here. This diagram shows the Hubble diagram. If we follow the line, these are the Hubble constant line. The data so far shows decreasing velocity towards the galaxy cluster and around this R_0 position, the velocity becomes almost zero, showing the zero velocity radius. Feeding the equations through this data, we can derive the value of Hubble constant first like this, like 66 plus or minus some errors. This is very strange. The value of a constant is derived this way. It's a very consistent method. It is TRGB calibrate. Pink region shows the collection of TRGB estimates for the Hubble constant and also Planck value in green. Totally independently derived values of constants which is encouraging. And then, we can also get the value of the R_0 velocity radius about seven mega parsecs or so. If you compare this value with the virial must commit comparable so this confirms that dark matter is mostly inside the radius. Using better TRGB data. With Roman and JWST, we can derive precise TRGB distances to the infall galaxies in the direction of galaxy clusters and groups closer than 30 mega parsecs or so. Then you can obtain the dark matter distribution around galaxy clusters and the value of the local Hubble constant. I lost my time. Okay. Am I going to fast? You have 10 minutes. Myung: 10 minutes, okay. You have another 15 minutes. Myung: 15 minutes, okay. Testing LCDM models in dwarf galaxies. Broad galaxies -- Breitbart galaxies range between ten to the seventh and ten to the ninth. Classical boards and the faintest samples of broad galaxies are called ultra-faint dwarf galaxies which are barely visible in the imaging of the previous ones. The range are smaller than those of globular clusters. We know there is a well-known problem which comes from the comparison between the luminosity derived from models and observations. This has been known for long. Also, if you see the current collection of lunar functions of the classical dwarfs around many galaxies given by Carson error, individuals in the left side, and the right

that it's a little bit more messy. They show diversity and the luminous functions and also broad scattered. The problem maybe related to this one. However, they covered up to only brighter than minus nine. We need to go to faint, which are the range of ultra-faint dwarf galaxies. The relation between external mass and the virial mass are uncertain as shown in the left figure and also in the right panel, you are seeing a comparison between the Milky Way and dwarf galaxy as functions. The lowest range for UFDs are very uncertain if we get a solid database for UFDs, then we can get a better understanding of the problems. UFDs, the faintest galaxies in the universe. First discovered from SDSS as in 2005 so it's one of the newcomers. They are faintest with the lowest stellar mass and also the smallest galaxies and they have the lowest metallicity. They are like a pristine relic from the early universe and so far they have been found mostly in the local group mainly around the Milky Way galaxy. But, these UFDs have intrinsically very low surface brightness and they are very small so they are -- it is so difficult to find them beyond the local group. However, astronomers found a view beyond the local group. In these group, three UFDs closer than the distance error. However, we have more. At a distance larger than 16 mega parsecs, once found in Virgo cluster and another one found in Fornax. There are no known UFDs between four mega parsecs and 16 mega parsecs so far. Thousands of UFDs in these ranges. By the way, these UFDs may be only present because of star formation in these galaxies and it about 12 galactic years ago. This can be anywhere, not only around the massive galaxies. Shown by simulations, 2019. Roman is on the ideal tour to survey such omnipresent UFDs if any. I'm going to show two examples of this in UFDs, the Virgo cluster. It shows the 18 SD field, so tiny. In this tiny field, there are one classical dwarf galaxy marked with a circle. We found one marked by red box shown here. You can see a small number of the point of sources actually members of a new galaxy. Looking at the first of our CMD of gnome broad galaxies and other CMD of a new UFD. They show very metal-poor. Showing that it is a genuine member of the Virgo cluster with a very low metallicity. In the case of Fornax, we took a chastity field around the galaxy. Not by the red circle. The red circle shows the location of a new galaxy. This shows that new galaxy. You see a small number of groupings of the stars. This is a galaxy. UFDs can be found at a distance of Fornax but we have only found one in each cluster. Here's right once and the yellow star, they are Virgo and Fornax so they are real UFDs. In the Virgo UFD and Fornax UFD are only the tip of the iceberg. You can do UFD survey of galaxy clusters in groups and fields. The results of stellar photometry, we can get the distances so they can get rid of the member of the cluster and the UFDs and also can derive them with color from metallicity. We can test the LCDM paradigms with UFD luminous functions and also test re-ionization quenching hypothesis. Then origin of intracluster here right. Again, image of the Virgo cluster. 38 SD field marked by small boxes and you see it covering the diffraction of the galaxy cluster. You can derive the CMD of the stars in Virgo at the distance of Virgo. And also you can compare those with M105. Eight SD field. If you see, the color decision what metallicity is in the function. Shows to peaks and then this MDF is very similar and our field of 105 showing that the origin of this are similar. All the results are based on only if you're a chastity feels so we need a much wider coverage. The Roman, large galaxies clusters and groups at a distance closer than 30 mega parsecs or so. You can tell the origin of the ICL and here right and a simple history of galaxy clusters as well as galaxies in each cluster. And the finally, global clustering. Before JWST, the nearest galaxy cluster with intracluster known is Virgo and the furthest is Abell 2744. This is a map of Virgo in the blue map. In the case of Abell 2744, comparing it with

visualizing from the model, finding some similarities in the tool. This is the only central part of the galaxy cluster so we need a wide-field imaging. We only need one field of imaging with Roman period finally, I'm going to introduce JWST view of globular clusters in a massive galaxy cluster. The famous image of a space cluster is a beautiful image. The center part. In the center part, we see many globular clusters. Also you can see the red box in the bottom left corner which is a globular cluster in the background galaxies. From this, you can derive the photometry of point sources and then you can select globular clusters. Finding from the comparison between bright galaxy region and the cluster region, the fraction of globular clusters is larger in the intracluster region showing that globular clusters in the intracluster region are mainly composed of metal-poor globular clusters. Also we can derive the radial density profile, finding two components, one close to the BCG component and the IGC component is much brighter. The yellow contours, map of a globular cluster. Some similarities and differences between images. Blue circles show's clubs without dwarf galaxies. You can compare also greater with a cleansing model map and also a contour map. They show some similarity. They can be a good trace of dark matter. Or you can compare this Intracoastal line map given by -- probably presents it. There is a very similarity between GC map. Although you can compare the map to the x-ray map. They show some differences. You can compare the radial profiles of a mass. The various lines show various matters so there are some discrepancies between matters. If you compare x-ray or GC, just a black line. In the inner part, they are very similar but the outer parts, they show some differences. With the JWST and women, we can map galaxy clusters at 0.5 to survey globular clusters. From this, we can study a simple history of galaxy clusters and distribution of baryon or dark matter. There are so many exciting cosmological projects with stellar population is to be provided by Roman and JWST. Some examples are presented here. Let's enjoy the gold3n era with Roman and JWST. Thank you for listening.

Thanks very much for a nice doctor to have some time for questions and we are not open it with in person questions and online questions. Start with and in person question. Please remember to introduce yourself. Because this is Adam Riess and that was a very nice talk. Thank you. The question I had. You should a calculation of doing Virgo in fall to try to get cosmography. My question was it seems like you're assuming Virgo as a perfect sphere but Virgo is pretty complicated. I think it has 3-meter sup clubs. I think my question is how sensitive is a calculation like that you arbitrary or different mass distributions than a perfect sphere. Myung: At this moment, I don't know the answer. However, I can imagine that we are looking at the galaxies far from the center of the galaxy cluster. Asymmetric distribution of mass in galaxy cluster may have an influence on these results. A better answer should be given from Madeline. Okay. It seems like maybe a good way forward that maybe would be relevant for Roman is that you would want your galaxy is all around Virgo. It looked like they were all in one -- they were all in the front side. It seemed like if you could compare the results all around, then you would have better confidence of whether the results depends on the mass distribution. Myung: Yes, it is great. At the moment, we don't have any online questions so if there are any other questions from the room, we can take those. Sticker hello. Very nice to talk. I noticed that this color diagrams with UFDs looked very sparse. I remember reading this paper that suggested that you get a robust measurement, you would need roughly 400 stars one magnitude before the TRGB. I wanted to ask if there was a plan accounting for the low number of stars to be measured in TRGB with the

CR DS. Myung: You mean my plan to Mexico if you had a plan. Or a suggestion if you were to do -- use the solar magnitude diagrams. Myung: First of all, I don't think I have a plan because I'm fading away but yeah. But surely we need to do tests in that regard. Here, presenting just a general properties. The test, yep. They should be given. Very good. Sounds like an exercise for the students. Thanks very much again. We are going to move on to our next speaker but thank you so much for joining us so late at night where you are. Myung: Thank you.

Adam Smercina: Revealing the merger histories of nearby galaxies from their stellar halos with Roman

You have 10 minutes. Excellent. Okay, great. I met, everyone. I am Adam Smercina. And I'm going to tell you today about a brief overview of what I think a renaissance in our understanding of the merger histories of nearby galaxies is going to look like with Roman and JWST. There we go. Okay. The merger history of galaxies -- There it is. Sorry about that. The merger history of galaxies are really important for us to understand, because we think mergers are a primary driver of galaxy evolution. To measure the merger history of galaxies, we are typically looking at the stellar halos of galaxies as a central prediction is galaxies marriage and larger galaxies create smaller galaxies, the form the stellar halos like you see here from the fire simulation. We spent sort of the last ten years or so kind of combining insight from galaxies simulations like this as well as observations from the ground and space to really try to understand what we can extract, the information that we can extract from the stellar measurements. The big thing that we have learned is that the largest merger that a galaxy has experienced in his lifetime dominates the measurable properties of stellar halos that you are able to measure. What can we then learn about these dominant mergers from these stellar lope measurements? We need to know the properties of the progenitor galaxy. We get this for measuring the properties of the accreted stars in the little prick we like to understand the time of the merger so that we might understand the impact that this merger has on central galaxy. This is the kind of schematic goal that we are trying to achieve. They have gone about this a couple of different ways. First of all, you can use kind of sparse HST fields giving you a small window on these accreted halos with very precise photometry. Also use a more wide-field approach using Widefield in the from the ground to study the halos like I'm showing here using the very most luminous evolves stellar tracers. These red giant branch stars, I'm showing a map of them in the stellar halos of the nearby galaxy. Very recent paper we put out detecting the super hyper supreme can. With these types of techniques, you could detect these very well as you can see down to very faint surface limits. This very beautiful radial of merger or remnant here in the stellar halo event. But there are some problems with measuring the properties from this kind of ground-based photometry. I want to illustrate some of these challenges by comparing to the single Hubble field that exists in this halo. The color magnitude diagram of the stars detected with Hubble is shown over here. You can see this beautiful -- with 2 very distinct populations. And of the blue stellar halo population to the left. You can distinguish these very well. You can do a pretty decent job at estimating these things. This color magnitude diagram is what happens if you translate this photometry to the depth and the filter coverage of our observations. All these great out things were stars that were detected with Hubble that would not be detected with -- we detect this nice fairly nice looking blue red giant branch. It is very hard to do kind of detailed measurements with this. You

can only infer for example very crude metallicity from this. I want to point out this is about the depth we are going to get. This is the very best basically that you can do from the ground. Not without a lot of pain. And so it is very clear that space-based imaging gives you much more robust measurements of these massive metallicity process. We have had to make this choice. Do we want the fidelity, or do we want the wide-field capability that we get from the ground? With Roman, we will no longer have to choose between these things. This is the first time we are going to have access to this high precision photometry over fields of view that are comparable to what we can do from the ground. I'm showing you an example here of a Roman field over top of this is featured in this M64 halo. It covers the entire thing in one go. And with only about an hour of an integration time per filter, you can get this lovely looking color magnitude diagram like I am showing over here is read filters. Resolve the entire evolved stellar population, entire red giant branch, you can do very precise measurements of the stellar halo properties. You can even reach the red clump which is this very information rich point of stellar evolution where you can even calculate detailed star formation histories over this entire halo. An example survey might look something like this. These are 20 Roman fields in this kind of rectangular pattern here. 2 filters, you can reach the red clump of depth or calculate detailed star formation histories Boris Taylor halo populations. Out to 100 kiloparsec's are so. This is something that has never ever been possible before. There were five or six or so of these Milky Way mass galaxies at this make up our distance range. With a week or two total investment of Roman, we can create half a dozen data sets such as this that are unmatched by anything that we have done from the ground for any galaxy really to date. We can even do pretty well for galaxies out beyond at this distance, ten meg up our and even greater. We may not be able to do this kind of detailed star formation analysis the same way we could do the near galaxies. We can leverage that kind of ratio of different evolved stellar population's. They are very bright in this near infrared filters that Roman will give us access to. I'm highlighting work at the University of Michigan in this collaboration. He has found this very tight relationship between the ratio of these are GP to AGP stars. The time of local group quiescent dwarf galaxies with very deep photometry. This is relevant for stellar halos as well. This gives you the quenching time of the dominant progenitor which tells you about when that merger occurred. We can do this out to kind of the edges of the local volume. The last thing I want to talk about is the impact that JWST is going to have on the science. It is going to be a game changer for -- we have heard in a few talks already. The example I want to use here is this central mosaic of the nearby galaxy M33. The 3-Vana, image from a cycle one proposal. We've got beautiful data of the center of this nearby galaxy H2 region beautifully. You can see individual bubbles here. We even from the very first time resolve the nuclear stark roster of M33 which has been an impossible task with JWST. This is a testament to the resolution and the sensitivity of JWST. To give a more quantitative example here, on the left is the color magnitude diagram that we obtained with the Hubble, the batter HST treasury program. An hour of total exposure time. This is the center of M33 in the same region that just showed. And then on the right is the color magnitude diagram that we extract from this same region with JWST. Only seven minute exposure. it goes 2 magnitudes are so deeper than Hubble is able to do. Mostly this is due to the resolution of JWST able to beat down the stellar crowding that so impacted the observations in the infrared. Also that exposure time is so much shorter. This combination of resolution and sensitivity that JWST has given us is going to give us easy access to these detailed star formation histories not

just in stellar halos of galaxies but the central disks of massive galaxies themselves which is something that it is always been really hard for Hubble to do. It's can it be this really important anchor for these studies with Roman particularly in the more distant galaxies where we may only have access to these kind of proxies instead of direct star formation histories. To summarize here, the era of wide and deep with Roman and JWST, Roman is going to give us measurements of stellar halos and other merger progenitors for those stellar halos throughout the local volume. Unprecedented sample sizes of these. It's can I be able to measure these globally right across the entire halo for these nearest galaxies. It's going to give us at least the ability to calculate merger times for these dominant mergers out the ten mega parsecs and beyond. JWST is going to give us these deep star formation histories not just in stellar halos but the central disks of these massive galaxies which allows us to connect the evolution of the central is going to be this important anchor for these more shallow but still very deep Roman studies. This era of Roman and JWST combined it's gonna be this unprecedented opportunity to understand the entire revolutionary histories and something that nothing else planned is can they be able to do. Now 30-meter telescopes. Roman is really going to be unique for this. We should do it. I will take questions. Thanks.

As last time, we will start with questions in the room if we have any. Are there other questions? I have a question. Okay, go ahead. We can start online and then we will go to Andrea. He will and there is a question online. He says things for the nice talk. From the end 33 JWST program, can you say definitively whether or not it has a weak bar or not? That is an interesting question. It is something I've been thinking a lot about. I have done some work on trying to look at the possible bar signatures with the HST photometry. It's even better in the center. Something I haven't looked at it yet. It is something that is definitely on our minds. You can see the photometry is much better. Yeah, it is an interesting question. Definitely something we are looking at. So I was very impressed about your ability to study quenching doing the small to large scale. This is fantastic. I was wondering if you also have some posts. Quenching timescales and properties may be a little bit different. Absolutely. I think specifically where this technique, this is going to be really powerful. Imagine getting out of things like 106 and 4258 which we know has an AGN. I think understanding the sort of quenching time for them merger timescale for the dominant merger that is responsible for these wins or whatever, I think that is something you could definitely do. If we get out out beyond ten mega parsecs, we can understand if the mergers correspond to this triggering time. I think that is fascinating. At the next speaker could come up and change over slides, we can have one more question is there one while we do that. If not, let's think Adam again. It's a very nice talk.

Nandini Hazra: Distances with Surface Brightness Fluctuations (SBF) and Globular Cluster Luminosity Functions (GCLF) with JWST and Roman

Our next speaker is Nandini Hazra. But again, you have 10 minutes. Hello. Good morning. PhD student at the Institute in Italy. And also at -- I work with -- right now I have been working with John at the lab for a few months working on my procedure. I work focuses on the indicators I have circled in red. I like to start my presentations with this outdated version of the extragalactic distance ladder. We made a lot of improvements on this. someone should get on that and make

a new graphic. The extragalactic distance ladder allows us to go from very local distances to very far distances. Having accurate distances allows us to calibrate masses and luminosity's other quantities much more accurately. And it might probably also have this result down the line. My work focuses on these two indicators. Primarily of the globular cluster luminosity in the 1010 mega parsecs. in the surface brightness misses. And we hope are there with numerous surveys. The idea behind the method is that when a galaxy is close to us, it looks more mobile than we can see more features and its underlying set up populations. The farther away it is, the more smooth this profile appears. The idea is to sort of calibrate the spatial fluctuation and use it to calibrate distances to these galaxies. And this was done for the first time in the late '80s. We have been using this method ever since. It turns out that it gives us. Accurate distances and individual distances as accurate up to 4%. And, we really like that because in recent years, we've had very accurate distances for very major discoveries for example the host for that dark matter for your galaxy. The first image, the most accurate distances to these three targets were calculated using SPF. I will give a very short and brief overview. This method is fairly complex and is not been very accessible. As such to the community due to that great complexity. It involves many steps of modeling, masking, and photometry which need to be done iteratively to get a high fidelity idea of what sources you are working with. Overall, there is a signal that is a ratio of the second to the first of the second of the first mode of the luminosity function. And how we get that is by modeling the galaxy profile, removing it and characterizing the residuals very accurately. One of the major sources of error for the ESB efforts signal comes from globular clusters. What this means is that the globular cluster population these galaxies need to be characterized very, very accurately in order to get a handle of what is this underlying fluctuation that is not coming from the underlying stars but from the globular clusters instead. The globular clusters themselves are actually shown to have had distribution which the peak of discussion distribution can be used as another distance indicator. Characterizing the globular cluster population these galaxies gives us a handle on the galaxy evolution properties but also the distance of itself with another separate indicator. And so this is work that we do characterizing the luminosity function in Hydro one using HST data. Our goal in this project has been to build a pipeline using open source tools and software's to make as you have distance measurement more accessible to the community. Eric collaborating using precursor data from the -- and also using data. Our overarching end game is to make operations of the ribbon when we have data from hundreds of thousands of galaxies. It would like to use this pipeline for globular clusters science. It's a data product that comes out very naturally and we can use it. If found in the process of doing this work that the pipeline we have built extends very well to other instruments that we were not expecting it to. One example I showed in the previous slide was the HST data. We have also used it on JWST which is something that I will show you a little bit now. So here is our favorite. We affect one galaxy in that frame which is right there in the magenta box. We have picked background frames around it to do a background -- we have used data in three short wavelength filters. This will allow us to have wider range of colors to go and look globular clusters and have not looks. The first step in doing this is to model and remove the galaxy profile. We have done this using -- we have done this in Python. Occasionally, we results when Python does not work super well for us. We are optimistic that we will iron out the kinks in that. This is one of the highest overheads in terms of time in our pipeline. The modeling takes a very long time to resolve. Masking and modeling is done iteratively so as to not let the very bright

objects mess with the signal. I'm going to flip back and forth between results of JWST and other instruments just a very briefly give you a glimpse of the capabilities of how we are working with this pipeline. We also get some intermediate calibration information from these images such as the -- and so on. This gives us a better and on the photometry we are doing in the frame. We are using a tool to do the photometry. Once you obtain the pressure corrections and correct it for them, we can go and look at their globular clusters and try and isolate them from the rest of the objects. The upper panel in the lower panel are two different bands. One is short and one is long. I would urge you not to look at the last on the right. I will come to that later. If you look at the first two frames on the left, I characterized the globular clusters by selecting them. At this stage using the compactness. Basically separating them very compact objects in the extended ones. I have done that using the concentration index which is the difference between and the magnitude between -- a very tight correlation that are different apertures not increase a lot. And I have also used a cluster which is a coming out of a tool which is an indicator. On the right, the other sources are: Print the sources I have identified are in purple. The first two panels on the left and middle. On the right is just showing all the sources detected in the frame. It can be a little confusing. I would be happy to chat about it later. It is not very visible when you look at all the objects together. What we do is we take only the objects that we are identifying is compact and within a certain magnitude range and we see that there is an immediate over density near that galaxy but some scattered objects around it. When we look at the color distribution of these objects, they immediately separated into distinct blobs. The golden objects on the left -- the purple ones are the ones I selected using the selection criteria as shown earlier for the purple objects we are hoping our globular clusters. What we are saying is that they agree very well with the theoretical models that shows us the color range in which globular clusters should live. They mostly lie within that blob. Well any good. We would also like to characterize the luminosity functions. We are seeing some interesting features which is that globular clusters in such a galaxy would usually show some sort of modality which could be a tracer of galaxy evolution or color banality relations. If we see this in photometry, we are also characterizing the luminosity function itself and large wavelengths which is never 4. We would be obtaining a globular cluster function distance which is farther than has been possible so far with other instruments. Once we characterize their globular clusters and have a better handle on that, it also allows us to go ahead and characterize the signal. We do this is by comparing the power spectrum of the residuals. When we remove the model from the image, we have the residuals. Can we match it in the image so this is one result that we have. We have compared the power spectrum is in the lower frame. The bottom right frame. Just above it with the squiggly lines is the spectrum of the galaxy. When we match the power spectra, what we get is a very good handle. We are still calibrating this for HSC and for , Future set is to go and look at this signal in the JWST frames where the signal is very much there. We can see it is much higher than in the background frames. What we need to do is go and calibrate it and make sure that we are not doing something serious with the imaging itself. I've conspicuously not spoken about Roman. Good to use my last minute to do that. As Adam said in the talk just before me that Roman is going to be the past. You don't have to choose. You can have wide area. When used to be done with 130 pointing's with HST can be done in seven. In 130 orbits can be done in seven pointing's using Roman. Roman would go farther, we go wider and wet sort of being a harvesting machine to get

distances, higher accuracy in the thousands. That has been the focus so far. And I will end with that intake questions.

That was really interesting. We have questions from in the room? Okay. Wait for the microphone. Remember to say your name. This is Adam. Just to give you a chance to talk a little bit more about Roman, there's a lot of galaxies to choose from. Where would you point? What would you target? One of the ideas now is to sort of go and just look at the wide area survey without choosing where to point. Our white paper is also outlined like a larger footprint. I don't think we have a very -- and I personally don't have a very big preference. One of the big that you can go look at other campaigns and that also gives you data within a certain distance. I would like to look at spherical. anyway there with Thanks. Checked if we have any online questions left me with There is one question online. As the Python code that was used for the simulation is available publicly at git hub or any other open source price? Nandini: There were no simulations and forget. We are still working on data. We hope to make the code available during the operations improvement so that is our in-kind contribution for Rubin. We will have to scale it up and we are working on that. Yes, it will eventually be available on get up so that you can go and get it by yourself. Because let's have a question in the room was the next speaker gets set up. Because of the work on trying to understand the globular cluster luminosity function starts with formation of clusters with a power law with a very steep slope and that its destructive processes that are debt into a galaxy so I wonder if anybody is modeled the remnants of those clusters, are they in some sense another contaminant to the SDF and has anybody tried to model it? Nandini: That is a very interesting question. I don't think people have modeled on what the remnants can look like. As a contaminant to the signal, I don't think so. You assume that they've been stripped farther away where the signal is so low that it doesn't even matter anymore. That would be really interesting to look at. Thanks. Let's thank Nandini again.

Mireia Montes: Unveiling the low surface brightness universe with Roman

Our next speaker is online. It looks like we are all set up and ready to go so thank you for joining us. Let me introduce Mireia Montes, who will be talking about low surface brightness universe with Roman. Mireia: Thank you very much. Hi, everybody. I would like to thank the organizers for giving me the opportunity to present it today. I am quite sad of not being able to be there with you all in Baltimore which was my previous home. The stock is somewhat loosely based on the white paper further survey that was omitted if you do so. I hope I will be able to prove to you that it's extremely interesting and worth exploring with Roman. If you are interested, this white paper is available in the archives. First, what are we referring to when we are speaking about the low surface brightness universe? surveys have revolutionized our understanding of the universe. As an example, being a white field survey, it enabled the study of the statistical properties of galaxies. However, this knowledge is biased toward the objects that you could observe. That means the brighter -- so towards more massive objects or massive galaxies. When we are referring to the low surface brightness universe, we are talking about the universe beyond what BSS was capable to observe. I'm talking about the optical, infrared wavelengths but it might be already quite obvious as we might be the only ones still talking about surface brightness. This encompasses many fields. For example, the study of the zodiacal light for understanding our

solar system. The Galactic heroes, the dust of our own galaxy, and also for instructors around stars that can tell us about stellar evolution and mass loss processes. However, where this field has "shown" what most of us are working on is this. We are missing the majority of low mass galaxies. At those lower masses is where we start seeing differences between the predicted and the observed number of galaxies. This difference is due perhaps to burrow metaphysics or external feedback that we are still not understanding very well or other more exotic explanations like different dark matter flavored spirit we do not only care about individual galaxies and studying the properties, but we basically need to observe them in numbers to populate the galaxy mass function. We also have the painted structures around not so faint galaxies. But we call the stellar heroes. In simulations, we should add as we grow fainter and fainter, we start seeing a plethora of structure that shows up around galaxies. Studying -- by studying the amount of light in these stellar halos and the ships of the structures within them, we can explore the low mass and of the galaxy mass function like what I was talking before. As well as the processes, the process or processes that shape the halo. In this case, observations have taken a little bit longer to catch up with what we see in simulations. We are starting to explore more and more of these faint structures around galaxies. Of course, if we are talking about the stellar halos, we have to talk about the most massive stellar halos that are what we call intracluster light or ICL. Not bound to any particular galaxy but float around following the potential of a cluster. This light is a byproduct of the interactions between the galaxies in the cluster. It contains the information of the things that have happened during the history of assembly of the cluster. This light is a powerful tool for understanding the formation and evolution of galaxy clusters. Not only that, this light has been shown to be an excellent luminous tracer of the dark matter distribution and clusters from galaxies. It is not a provides a picture of how dark matter distributes in these clusters. And how that matter distributes in clusters of galaxies is a consequence of the nature of that dark matter. Therefore, the intracluster light can also be a powerful tool for understanding dark matter. This is the low surface brightness universe that we can explore with Roman. Low surface brightness galaxies, stellar halos and intracluster light. I hope I have convinced, although it was a little bit rushed, but I hope I have convinced you of the interest in doing so, and exploring these low surface brightness universe. The problem is that to explore all of this, we need very deep observations and that comes at the cost of the objects that we can explore. We have only been able to explore the tip of the iceberg of that, what this can give us. That is where Roman comes into play, specifically the high latitude wide area survey. Applies to any Roman observation. The high latitude wide area survey will provide a very deep infrared view with HST like resolution. Exploring the infrared is very important in this regime. As we cannot get a spectroscopy and it might be that we might not be able to get ever a spectroscopy of these objects. To study the stellar population committee is very important to have also the infrared view. The special resolution is very important to minimize contamination and blending. Also adding the capability to resolve halo starts up to the Virgo distances and also study globular clusters as we have seen in previous talks. This survey will be a game changer for studying the low surface brightness universe, even allowing to explore it not so locally as to what we've been doing before but also at higher resolutions and see how it evolves with time. Very importantly, it will be around 2,000 square degrees, providing the area and therefore the numbers that we so desperately need. In order to show you what Roman will be capable to do, I will now talk about the study that we published last year, exploring the intracluster light in the

first images released of the JWST. I think that all of you know about this image, that this is the clusters. Thanks to the infrared view and their solution of JWST, we have seen a percentage view of the ICL of this cluster. As you can see here, we have been able to see all this structure, the plumes in the center, these tidal streams in the outer parts of the cluster that we haven't been able to see before. To do that, to explore the intracluster light, we had to do some image processing in order to take full advantage of the image. But I think my colleague Alejandro Borlaff will take in more detail in a second. Even that, we have also modeled wavelength coverage of the cluster. We can structure the color profiles of the cluster from the inner parts up to around 300 kiloparsecs. But we can see is in the inner parts, we have the process starts in the intracluster light is a major merger. You can see by the plumes in the image and also by the flat gradient in the colors. The major merger of the BCG or the brightest cluster galaxy with this companion and I hope that you can see my cursor here. This is what happens in the inner parts. In the outer parts, it seems that it's creating or forming the intracluster light in this cluster at the tidal stripping of satellites of a mass similar to the Milky Way. This is what we call the giant West Loop. Also you can see here in the eastern part of the cluster with this and this tidal stream. In summary, with the JWST, we've been able to see the diversity of processes that are building the intracluster light. It's just only a cluster so we need Roman in order to explore more and more clusters. I leave you with the QR code for the white paper and if you can take -- if you take anything from this talk, I hope it is that the low surface brightness universe is an important piece to understand how galaxies form and evolve. Thank you very much.

Thank you very much, Mireia. We have some time for questions. We'll start in the room. Do we have any? Are there any online questions? There are not? All right, maybe we are ready to hear from Alejandro.

Alejandro Borlaff: Below the iceberg, low surface brightness astronomy with HST, Euclid, and Roman

Our next speaker is Alejandro Borlaff on low surface brightness astronomy. Alejandro: My name is Alex. I'm here to talk about low surface brightness astronomy with HST, Euclid, and Roman. Okay. Ever since the very, very first simulations in the '70s, we know that the remains of the galactic allocation of the universe are in the very low and dark regions around the largest galaxies. Magnetic field is dependent on the parameters. Where are these things can make when we the data, for example, this galaxy, you see 1380 to appear. Nothing very special. And then this is a 26.5. When we push a little bit further, 1.5 magnitude deeper, we see that this galaxy is in fact one of the largest super brightness galaxies ever. In a spiral disk of 80 kiloparsecs. There is a great deal of morphology that we don't know at the very low end. Even galaxies like this one that apparently an ultra-thin isolated galaxy, this is the work of one of my students. Believe it or not, there is a warp in that region and one of the possible responsible is of this is a galaxy pulling the material in this image. So, we are only seeing the deep of this beautiful iceberg. Just to put some skill, we are starting to see the signs of the super brightness galaxies and ultra diffuser galaxies, stellar strips, tidal tails, magnitudes of 29, intracluster light, picking up some signal an inner and outer stellar halos and maybe someday we will break the limit and be able to see the remains of the cosmic web. I don't need to introduce this beautiful

image, but what I would like to focus is in a lower surface brightness details of this. It is extremely valuable because we know now that this whole cluster was shadowing galaxies in the size of the Milky Way. Great effort in trying to construct this information from the real images because we have lots of idioms and systematic effects that make separating the signal from the real signal from the systematic effect extremely, extremely hard. This is something that took a titanic effort to get this image corrected in a way that we could use it for a science. The problem is that by applying all these corrections over the images, we are losing a lot of information from the optimum potential of the images. The theoretical limit of these images will be about 31.2 magnitudes per square second period it depends on the size of what you want to detect. Due to this gradient, the limit of the dash the scientific research on this paper is 28. That's bad. That's really bad because that means that we are losing all these interesting parts were exactly Roman is going to be picking up a huge advantage. Roman will be able to come in theory, will be able to take structures from 29, 30 magnitudes per second is. The terminus breaks to the 31 magnitudes per square second limit. We need to get this on. Were these gradients are coming from to make the gradients by the fluff. If you take -- if you imagine that you are in your holidays and you want to take a picture of your favorite museum and there's a bunch of tourists, knowing, moving around and you don't want to be in your picture, you can take many images and average them and they are gone. We demonstrate that the words using the light as the background to retrieve them from the image without using the dash without using units which can introduce gradients. That is only one. Three lights is great for pictures but horrible for astronomy. We need to get rid of this. It's really hard because it depends on the photometry and the position of the sources around the view and inside the field of view. This is one image from HST that I really like which shows Titan and Saturn and you can see the stray light from certain getting inside the field of view. This is a PSF but this is different. This is the NDI. How good is your telescope in blocking the light outside the field view? If you know it, if you know this function depending on the degree and the wavelength and everything, you, in theory, you should be able to model and correct the gradients including ghosts. Everything. We need to do that. Why we need to do that? This is all for correcting the ground. The problem is you can mess with the background on the images themselves but that doesn't work for things that are very large. If you have large objects and systematic gradient and the gradient is the order of the size of the thing that you want to detect and measure the background in his images, you are going to enter the parts of this galaxy in the background model and you end up with an image which is oversaturated. This is the stark reality. You can see how there is background on negative comes around this extended galaxy cluster with the intracluster light should be. This is something that we need to correct. Without using the stray light direction and only using stellar mapping, more careful sky back in construction, we were able to recover and you can see the limits and the 29 magnitude, a function after version of the image. This is the field and you can see how the galaxy is twice the size using the same data. Using the same observation. This is a suboptimal. Ideally, we would like to know exactly how bright it is. How bright are these stars, where they are, what is the emission from the sun and moon, the earth, remove it. Then get to the galaxy or whatever that we want to detect in the field. Further, we need to normalize. This is exactly what we are doing from HST. To reconstruct the normal detector of gradients for this very complicated setup. If we succeed, we will be able to collect all these gradients from the sun, moon, stars, and generate a product, back on models that we used to create better sky background

correction and images. We are starting by using using models in Australia. This is not on the same scale. You can see that we are, without using the image, we are able to get the background in this galaxy. We are using extreme observations from HST. This is very close to the Sirius Star to model the NDI and the amount of light that we receive from this object is a function of how separated are we from the large object. We model and we hope that we will be able to do it using this detector. We were able to on the NDI provided by the engineering team to generate models, provided you have this gradient pixel for pixel. The idea would be to apply this to Roman. We have a very large field of view compared to JWST and HST give it very interesting extension in the spectral range. The idea would be to apply all this and get all this ready before Roman launches. Hopefully, we'll be selected for the proposal. I would like to finish with this image from the SDSS. You can see here some stray light gradient which limits the signal that we get in this image. We push a little bit further, this is what it will look like if we apply all these techniques to retrieve things that are a bit larger than a galaxy. To review with my conclusions, thank you very much.

Speak up beautiful images and on. Looks like we immediately have a question in the room. Great. Hi. Garrett Gilbert. Very nice to get my question is you're getting for the model to do this with Roman. I assume you will need some on sky observations to calibrate it. Will you be able to do self calibration is, do you think, with just a survey data that will be taken anywhere or do you think you need to do specific, pointed observations to calibrate it? Alejandro: That's a very good question. When we did this project for Euclid, one of the conditions was that we couldn't move the telescope at all. You had to use the data because that's not movable. All these that we developed for generating the model on the assumption that we won't be able to use anything else. If we are able to point out telescope and rotate it around bright objects and use the moon to measure the orbit, that will be absolutely great. One other idea is that if this stuff in connection, depending on how bright the light is and by definition, you always want to point to the regions where the zodiacal light is less bright. For calibration, it would be fantastic to have a program to point this to a very bright part of the sky and use it as a doom. We cannot have it down but we can have the zodiacal light but yeah, it will be very important. Speaker we don't have anything online. Any more questions in the room? I'm going to switch over to the next speaker. Because really nice blog. Thank you. I apologize how I missed this but what makes Roman so much better at this low surface brightness science than for example you should with JWST and SMACS? Alejandro: These get harder and harder and harder when you get if you are a few that is never because example, imagine that you try to come on your HST, .2 Andromeda and you had diffuse emissions. You didn't know where you're zero is. You have a very large field of view, you can do that. It's way easier when you get a large field of view. That makes all these waiver to use that. Roman would be absolutely fantastic. I see. Thank you.

Mainak Singha: A search for AGN in Green Peas in the local universe

Our next speaker should be online. Yes. We can see you. Perfect. All right. You should have 10 minutes and I'll interrupt you at 10 minutes. And who are you? This is Mainak Singha who is going to talk about AGN in Green Pea's in the local universe. Mainak: Hi, everybody. It's me from NASA Goddard. We are going to be talking about Green Peas and the local universe. an

extreme emission line galaxies. seen at about 0.3. Extreme properties and especially, they are usually seen as a green -- there sciences 0.3 kiloparsec. It's the reason they been called a Green Pea galaxy. It's incredibly important to understand. Because they share so many similarities. With their high-Z Lyman-alpha emitters. Sunnis found that the size is the half-light radius. Exactly similar to what you'd -- they basically sit in a similar metallicity range. The optical spectra is totally identical. As of this Green Pea galaxy is like a fossil from the era of reionization. It's really important to study them because they are going to give us information at the low redshift. . What drives the re-ionization? Long-standing debate. In 2015, there was a beautiful paper suggesting, the low luminosity. The redshift 4 to 6. They can mostly dominate the re-ionization energy budget. There little contribution from the star-forming galaxies. That's interesting because -- our star-forming galaxies are the main reason for the re-ionization. Obviously there are many people who have suggested that a massive galaxy, it might drive the re-ionization. There's a lot of controversy going on. What is the main cause of the re-ionization? We really want to find out if there's, AGN, and the role of AGN in re-ionization. There is a recent paper in 2023. Use the -- you see in the central panel they have found a broad line region. On the lower panel, I am showing you unified AGN models. The broad line region is usually hidden, type 1, type 2. You get to see it. When you are seeing such a broad emission line, it's giving you an indication we have AGN there. It's not a little redshift galaxy. It's the similar redshift range model predicted 4 to 7. They also added that this AGN could provide up to 50% of the photons in the re-ionization budget which means there may be a significant AGN contribution in the re-ionization process. It's crucial to understand what is AGN doing? What is the relation between AGN and Green Peas? If you look at the right panel, I have put -- I have shaded the region where Green Peas usually lie in the diagram. So the AGN galaxies from the Harikane example and the Green Pea galaxies are sharing similar space in the diagram. Not only that, a study in 2022 suggested Green Pea galaxies also have AGN. It's really worth it to study any possible evidence of AGN to understand what's going on in the realization process. The contribution in the re-ionization process. That's why really want to find out if there's any AGN in Greenpeace. So what we do, we look through the data archive and found there are only four Green Peas with detectable x-ray emission. But we also found two other Greenpeace showing infrared variability. I am showing you in the top right panel. The light curve is changing. AGN are basically thought to be variable across the electromagnetic spectrum. You don't see optical variability. You see mid infrared variability. So what this suggests, if there is a AGN, it's obscured. We may extrapolate that. Many sources. We need to extrapolate that to a conclusion that Green Peas might harbor optically obscure AGN. We have another line of evidence. What we find, this diagram, we find Greenpeace are basically following in a region which is coincident with quasars. They have been thought to harbor. Other optical infrared, and every wavelength. Starburst galaxies would cause these colors. The problem is they need to have really high ionization parameters. For they Green Peas, the ionization parameters much lower than the galaxies need to have. Therefore basically the conclusion of the different color, not any stellar feedback processes. Much more far from the source such as an a GM. Looking into the data, we find something really interesting. The observed luminosity that you see on the panel, it's six times higher than one would expect. We are taking the contribution for the low mass and the high mass exit binaries. Could we explain if I just those two? Okay. Exit binaries thought to be the contributor. They are not. Where are the emissions coming from? May be a massive black

hole. Not only that, if we go into the optical data -- sorry. I am going to move this one around. We find that the number of photons that you use to produce the emission cannot be explained by that contribution. The companion stars. With classical signature. Having a prominence. The stars may drive the helium 2 emission. But what we would expect cannot just fully explain the helium 2 mission we are seeing here. There has to be some of the contribution. About only that, in the spectra, one would expect the spectra to be broadened. The helium II. Velocity dispersion. We are also seeing there is no carbon 4058. The conclusion that maybe it's not the stellar feedback process causing all of this line of evidence. Has to be a massive black hole. We want to be cautious here. For the x-ray emission. We have a study suggesting the wind from the superstar cluster would generate x-ray mission. The contribution by factor of 2. It's 10 minutes. Sure, perfect. We wanted to find the maximum amount of contribution. So we added the contribution and the stellar wind. A three-member from the previous slides. The luminosity is six times. If you add them together, you seem the observed x-ray luminosity is just over twice, the XRB plus wind. In other words, the stars are so many contribute 50% of the observed x-ray emission. So where does the other 50% come from? There has to be another stellar source that has to be powerful enough to give rise to those emitted infrared colors through all the spectra. Therefore the most reasonable conclusion there has to be an active nuclei which is doing all of these. What if there is an active galactic nuclei? We use the simulation spike. Suggesting in AGN feedback, the mechanical energy output is similar to the luminosity of AGN. So for our samples, that has to be the mechanical energy output from the AGN in Green Peas if they do exist. Obviously we probably need even more stringent evidence to make a major conclusion. All of this line of evidence. Not just stars. You need something else to make, to connect all these dots. That's the reason we are trying to find Green Peas not only in this example but a martial -- much larger size. That is where Roman comes from. Roman hats this 0.26 square degrees. The near infrared wavelength range. All of the heating lines. Find whether it's green peas or. We can probe millions of Green Peas. So in this range we can actually find out what's happening from the end of the Cosmic Dawn Center the prison days. To the present days. Green Peas can give us so much information. We will be able to do so much more statistics. Thanks so much, Mainak. I think I need to cut you off. We are at time.

We have time for a very quick question while the next speaker gets set up. A quick question. Have you looked at radio variability? We have seen. Basically what we were trying to do, apply the observations. There is some data for Green Peas. That is our next go to to look at the radio observations and see what's going on. It's the next thing to do.

Jenny Greene: Massively multiplexed spectroscopy with the Prime Focus Spectrograph in the era of JWST and Roman

All right. I know I am the last talk before lunch. I am a bit of a departure from the rest of the session but it's been a wonderfully interesting session. Happy to be part of it. I'll be talking about probing cosmic noon with what is now a soon to start survey with the prime focus spectrograph which we just got data with the near-infrared arm a month or two ago so I'm hopeful we will start the survey in 2024. You can see we are a very wide area spectrograph. What you need to know, 1.4-degree diameter field of view with 2400 fibers, each about an arc

second. We cover 3800 Ångströms to 1.26 microns. It's really massively Multiplex spectrograph. That should be very powerful for galaxy evolution particularly around cosmic noon were historically there has been a redshift desert. PFS will have three main science pillars. A BAO survey. Cosmology survey of local group dwarfs and the halo of the Milky Way and Andromeda and the galaxy evolution survey that I'll be talking about. There's lots of themes that I think are well aligned with the goals of the high latitude survey. Relaying this is just an extended infomercial for PFS. Want to make sure the community knows it's coming. We love to promote the idea that the highlighted survey includes the PFS fields. So we will be in three of the four hyper supreme camera deep fields. Ex-MM-L assess, deep 2-3. Because most. We've worked extremely hard to have uniform. We will be selecting -- this is a nice one slide summary of the survey. We are looking to get 250,000 galaxies that redshift 1.5 to 2. Looking for and I GM survey. Background galaxies will probe the I GM. To me like thousand dropouts. We spanned over wide redshift range with our wide spectral coverage. We expect to be able to probe both environments. Detailed physical properties of these galaxies at all redshifts. This is our attempt to find the parameter space where PFS really shines. Spectral resolution adopted from this. Versus the number of objects. You see we live in a really nice corner parameter space. Rich astrophysics and lots of objects. So what would be super great is to also have the imaging data in these fields from Roman. There's a lot more science we can do, extending H alpha out to the edge of our Continuum selected sample. We will provide information. We are excited about having detailed morphologies for the galaxies and PFS. It's amazing. It's people with the best you can do from the ground. We won't be able to resolve most of the PFS galaxies with the data, although it's great for selection. We can do that with Roman. Lots of good science to do. One example would be the alignments. Just thinking about ways that are spectral coverage is interesting and complementary. Those are examples. Expected PFS just to give you a visual impression of all of the important lines that we are covering over these redshift ranges. We will have a H-alpha sample to redshift 0.9. Hopefully that can help calibrate the Grism decomposition of H-alpha and nitrogen 2. Giving us H-alpha would be super exciting. Finally, there's also a lot of interest in the PFS group and re-ionization. We have narrowband surveys already. We will be following those up really to look at the morphologies of lineman-Alpha to try to understand it, the re-ionization. You can't really do this with low resolution spectra. All the fun stuff that Lyman-a does. That is the short pitch for why it would be really nice for the community to have HLS quality data in the PFS deep fields. I'm going to take one or two more minutes to promote to other science things that I'm excited about. One, we heard a lot about SPF today so I don't have to explain. My student is thinking hard about SBS galaxies. You saw the thesis, the luminosity studies that we did with ELVES. The trick is the populations are much more luminous. Lets you get further out that you can do with the optical but you have to be able to calibrate that. So the idea is if you have LS ST colors, can you get a tight relation. Please check out his poster. He looks at the numbers we could hope to get and some promising looks at stellar population models. The other thing I wanted to talk about now, going to the opposite redshift regime, this work we have been doing with uncover to look for the moderate luminosity. We have heard quite a bit about this yesterday. We got interested because we had this lens, little red dot that Furtak published. It's so compact. We can put a 30 parsecs size limit on it. It's very red. And so it's one of the reddest things in the uncover field. The other reason we got excited, this beautiful broad H L5. You can see there is some UV light that is incredibly red. We also had deep ALMA. Export

way not the best explanation. We think these are moderate luminosity HGN. This is the luminosity function here. They have brought H-alpha, Grism data. You can see that it flattens and the little red dots are here. They seem to be the moderate luminosity population, they are just too faint. The question is, we would love to exploit wider areas to find larger numbers. Is there a clever way that we can use Roman to find them. There were hints already from Spitzer. This is a paper by Mark Lacey. Showing that this type 1, red tie population, their numbers are rising as you go to redshift 3. Ships with JWST, they were following over these things. It's an interesting question. I will leave you with a beautiful PFS footprint and take questions.

Thank you for a very nice talk, as usual. Do we have questions? Did I go too fast? Hi. Adam. I wanted to go back to that slide where you were talking about calibrating the FPS. It's kind of obscured. The overlap region, I'm assuming you're targeting the stellar mass Access set by galaxies themselves. We have to detect them. I wonder of the stellar halos, nearby stellar halos close to the disk where things aren't crowded. It might be an interesting target to add to this as well. We are focused on works but there's quite a lot of science to do. Interesting, thank you. One of the things we are excited about digging into is how much information we are going to get as well. We don't currently have any online questions. I am very excited about your red dots. I have a question about, we have masses for the black holes. They are around 10 to the 7. Aunt Harikane too. The objects are similar. Our luminosities, if you click redden, they are consistent. There's one super exciting source magnified, very magnified. Below 10 to the 43. I am super excited to see. Uncover just submitted. We are getting spectra at the end of July. We could get redshifts for all of these. We'll see. I said that they were very compact. The thing that's exciting for us to do once we have redshifts is black hole to galaxy ratios. It's very hard to find a galaxy here except a little bit sometimes. Altogether. I don't know. We are moving into a regime where the masses more than 10% of the mass of the galaxy. JWST. Really compact. Looks like we have a question in the front. Back to PFS. For the IDM tomography map map, I am wondering if you want to combine that with lensing from Roman. Is there anything that you do with Roman than the high latitude wide-area survey? Can you do lensing at redshift 2? That's sort of why I'm asking. If we go deeper. That's a good question. I didn't think depth was the limiting factor. You tell me. I don't know. Presumably they are background sources. Maybe for a question tomorrow. You presumably want to map at the same redshift of the tomography map. I think it is a depth thing. If it's a deft thing, then we should be able to solve it. Last question. I might've missed this with the kerfuffle at the beginning but when this -- when are they doing the observing? We just got their -- near infrared information. We are on track to start 2024. The Subaru community for various reasons is not interested in science validation time. The G.E. survey will be spending our first year doing science validation, trying to understand her selection. We -- our goal is to have at least 2,000 12 hour super deep spectra. That's what we are going to go for. Everybody, think happy thoughts. Exciting times.

Join me in thanking all of our speakers again online and in person. Do the organizers need to say anything before lunch or do we just go to lunch? Saying something about the discussion groups. There are new slack channels with the topics that we discussed yesterday. Please put your notes so that the people online can see what the discussions were in person and we can combine them for a successful summary session Friday. Thank you.

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